

Potential microgrid model based on hybrid photovoltaic/wind turbine/generator in the coastal area of North Sumatra

Habib Satria^{1,2}, Rahmad B. Y. Syah^{2,3}, Dadan Ramdan^{1,3}, Muhammad Khahfi Zuhanda³, Jaka Windarta⁴, Syafii⁵, Almoataz Youssef Abdelaziz⁶

¹Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Universitas Medan Area, Medan, Indonesia

²Excellent Centre of Innovations and New Science-PUIN, Engineering Faculty, Universitas Medan Area, Medan, Indonesia

³Department of Informatics, Faculty of Engineering, Universitas Medan Area, Medan, Indonesia

⁴Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, University of Diponegoro, Semarang, Indonesia

⁵Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Universitas Andalas, Padang, Indonesia

⁶Department of Electrical Power and Machines, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Future University in Egypt, Cairo, Egypt

Article Info

Article history:

Received Feb 6, 2024

Revised Feb 24, 2024

Accepted Feb 26, 2024

Keywords:

Diesel generator

HOMER pro

Microgrid

Photovoltaic

System hybrid

Wind turbin

ABSTRACT

The high potential for renewable energy in the North Sumatra region, especially the coast of the Belawan area, needs to be exploited properly. The design will be carried out to explore the potential in coastal areas by carrying out simulation models of microgrid systems and hybrid system-based electricity installations. The method that will be used is to find the accuracy of strategic location points by considering the weather around the plant. The aim of determining strategic and ideal microgrid installation location points is useful in building a reliable system when fluctuating climate conditions occur so that it will have a significant effect on energy balance and energy conversion. The potential for installation construction will be carried out with a hybrid system using power sources from photovoltaic (PV), wind turbines and diesel generators assisted by HOMER pro software. Real measurement results in the field were obtained for the installation of a hybrid-based microgrid system on PV with a DC output power of 618.80 W with measurements in sunny weather conditions, then the potential wind speed on the wind turbine reached 5 m/s and the potential use of a diesel generator reached 40% with a power output capacity 1 kW.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Habib Satria

Excellent Centre of Innovations and New Science-PUIN, Engineering Faculty, Universitas Medan Area

Kolam St, No.1, 20223 Medan, Indonesia

Email: habib.satria@staff.uma.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

The high potential for developing renewable energy source installations in the Sumatra region should be exploited appropriately [1]–[3]. This is inseparable from the depletion of fossil fuels in the future and the shift of the world community towards awareness of environmental impacts that are cleaner than pollution [4]–[7]. The most efficient technology is installed according to community needs in meeting current electricity availability with an integrated system in operation and control using a microgrid system [8]–[11]. Then, to develop the electrical power supply to be more optimal, a hybrid system was added, which means it is the most ideal combination in supporting the power increase system and reliability system in the microgrid. [12]–[15]. The coastal area of the city of Medan, especially in the North Sumatra region, is a strategic area if a hybrid model-based microgrid system is installed involving the integration of photovoltaics (PV) sourced from solar energy, wind turbine installations sourced from wind energy and also the installation of diesel

generators [16]. Coastal areas include areas that have quite high intensity of sunlight and also have wind speeds which can later be a solution in moving wind turbines continuously [17]–[19]. However, irregular weather fluctuations in the city of Medan based on data from the meteorology climatology and geophysics council (BMKG), have caused the percentage of potential power output of renewable energy installations to decrease. Therefore, the study for the installation was diverted to the point with the most potential, namely the coastal area, for the installation of an integrated hybrid system from renewable energy [20]. The potential impact that will result is the stability of electrical power which is very influential in the use of electrical energy and also the effect of being free from shadows which will make the conversion of energy from the sun more optimal [21]–[23]. The microgrid technology that will be used is compatible with inputting potential local renewable energy resources such as solar and wind power. Then this system will be able to provide distributed generator connectivity as a buffer unit, and the loads are interconnected with each other [24]–[26]. The hybrid microgrid installation system also has advantages in terms of economy and efficiency compared to other microgrid architectures [27], [28]. However, microgrid injection on microgrid performance must be reviewed because it affects the overall dynamic performance of the microgrid [29]–[31]. Then also, it should be noted that with the increasing need for electricity every year and conventional energy reserves getting smaller, it is impossible to depend completely on conventional energy [32]. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct an analysis first on new and renewable energy power plants to find out whether the power plants are efficient and able to replace conventional energy power plants in the future [33]. The potential that will be reviewed is the PV installation system, wind turbine and diesel generator installations carried out in the coastal area of the city of Medan.

2. METHOD

The model simulation will be carried out with 3 power generation system configurations, namely, PV system configuration, wind turbine and diesel generator. Meanwhile, the battery is used as backup storage when there is a voltage drop caused by the intensity of sunlight. The method is carried out by serving in the field using a lux meter, anemometer with validation margin of error testing using an Android application. Then the experimental data is carried out in real time in the field by installing PVs in the coastal zone. In a diesel generator installation, it operates and produces electrical power using fuel injection, with estimates not being the main generator. PV systems and wind turbines are the main energy supply sources for residential areas. The simulation used uses HOMER pro software and for PV energy conversion analysis uses real field data with a PV output power installation of 650 Wp. HOMER Pro software is used to design and simulate microgrid systems with the advantage of being able to estimate the technical feasibility and energy conversion of previous developments in renewable energy production. Simulations using HOMER pro software for microgrid system configuration in the coastal area of Belawan, North Sumatra are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Microgrid system in a hybrid model of renewable electricity generation in coastal areas

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Configuration and analysis of energy production operating using a renewable energy system with a hybrid integrated microgrid system in coastal areas in North Sumatra, Indonesia. The microgrid system with a hybrid model is research targeting the Belawan area, located on the coast of North Sumatra. In terms of natural resource potential and enriched with the availability of wind and solar power, energy conversion can be carried out optimally. To operate the HOMER pro software simulation, it is necessary to prepare several required data, including load requirement data, weather condition data and technical data for each system component. The tracking location for microgrid sites on the coast of North Sumatra is shown in Figure 2.

irradiation. Using this simulation helps to see the intensity of sunlight in various conditions such as sunny, cloudy and overcast. The accepted temperature for the intensity of solar radiation for the coastal areas of Medan city is almost 40 degrees Celsius, but this temperature will of course affect the energy conversion generated by PVs as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4. Cartesian coordinate system location point

Figure 5. Potential for hot surface temperatures in the coastal area of Belawan, North Sumatra

3.3. Potential speed of wind energy

The drive for a wind turbine requires wind with a vertical axis of rotation or a horizontal axis. The potential for wind energy is very abundant, especially in the coastal areas of Belawan, North Sumatra. This can of course be used as a renewable energy source to fill electricity needs if exploited properly. One of the effects of the number of wind turbine angles on power and coefficient of power (COP) can increase electrical energy conversion d. The measurement results using wind speed simulations are still relatively low with a force reaching 5 m/s. Simulation of test results using a horizontal wind turbine. Figure 6 shows the potential location of wind speed and wind turbine installations in the coastal area of the Belawan area.

Figure 6. Potential wind speed and wind turbine installation in the coastal area of the Belawan area

3.4. Potential fuel generator installation

Microgrid specifications in the Belawan coastal area use fuel price adjustments with a capacity of 1 kW with an estimated usage of 40% due to prioritizing renewable energy generation. Then the high cost of diesel generators further reduces generator fuel consumption as well as reducing gas emissions to help supply power to the load. Therefore, the design of a hybrid system in a microgrid is a particular choice as a better option than a system using a generator. Diesel generator utilization and fuel efficiency curve are shown in Figure 7.

The use of diesel generators does not reach 100% because it is a supporting factor as a backup electricity source that can be used to meet electricity needs that cannot be met by renewable energy sources. Therefore, the efficiency fuel consumption calculation is calculated using output power estimates for a reference capacity of 1 kW with the application of household electricity supply in the coastal area of Belawan, North Sumatra. The components used in the configuration are analyzed in the utilization of the fuel consumption efficiency curve shown in Figure 8.

Figure 7. Fuel curve efficiency

Figure 8. Curve Efficiency fuel consumption

3.5. Photovoltaic energy conversion testing

Retrieving solar energy conversion system data from PVs aims to monitor the conversion and system reliability resulting in a more optimal microgrid system output. The panel used has a capacity of 650 Wp with a polycrystalline type connected in parallel. The optimization system still uses the PV position when conditions are flat. This energy conversion is still not optimal, but the initial research was set with PV conditions at 90° to the direction of the sun, but later to make the PV installation conditions more optimal, a tracker system will be used and supported by calculating azimuth angles and elevation angles. The data entered is the coordinates of the Belawan Coastal area, North Sumatra, taking into account longitude and latitude. The results of energy conversion in coastal areas using real field measurement data and then converted using assisted applications are shown in Figure 9.

Based on the graph of the accumulated output frequency of PV energy conversion installations in the coastal area of Belawan, North Sumatra, the DC voltage frequency graph in Figure 9(a), the output results from the intensity of sunlight using lux meter reached 162,000 lux. Then in Figure 9(b), when measuring PV conditions in a flat position, the DC voltage output is 45.4 Volts with a standard deviation of 1.72. During the monitoring period, the output voltage on the PV showed irregularities in the coastal areas of the Belawan area due to weather fluctuations. Then the data is displayed as in Figure 9(c). In the current graph, the peak DC current is 13.63 A with a standard deviation of 3.704. For the last image, Figure 9(d), it is a source of energy conversion using maximum conditions occurring at 2.00 pm, amounting to 618.80Watt DC with a standard deviation of 166,904 with flat PV installation conditions. During the monitoring period, the output power of the PV showed irregularities due to climate change, resulting in changes in power caused by sunlight not being focused on the surface of the PV.

Figure 9. Graph of accumulated output frequency of PV energy conversion installations in the coastal area of Belawan, North Sumatra; (a) frequency of lux meter output, (b) frequency of PV voltage, (c) frequency of PV current, and (d) frequency of PV power

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the potential of the microgrid system by modeling hybrid PVs, wind turbines and diesel generators using simulation results in the HOMER Pro software, the greatest potential is by installing PVs because the intensity of sunlight is very high. This is still in a flat position, where energy conversion should be more optimal by using an active tracking system to find the sun's focal point. Then the potential of wind is also very promising as an energy reserve to supply more electricity loads than diesel generators. The results of real data measurements in the field obtained data for the intensity of sunlight reaching 162,000 lux, measuring PV conditions in a flat position with a DC voltage output of 45.4 Volts with a standard deviation of 1.72, a peak DC current of 13.63 A with a standard deviation of 3.704 and also the output power Maximum conditions occurred at 2.00 pm at 618.80 Watt DC with a standard deviation of 166,904. This is still not optimal because when the sun is perpendicular to the surface of the PV panel, clouds cover the surface of the panel so that peak power is obtained at 2.00 pm which should occur in the time range from 11.00 am to 1.00 pm. The intensity of the wind speed measured in the Belawan coastal area reaches 5 m/s so that the installation of a wind turbine can produce optimal electrical energy.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to thank the Foundation Internal Fund (DIYA) for financial support with Grant No. 1816/LP2M/03.1.1/VI/2023. We also thank the Medan Area University for supporting this research. And research collaboration with Universitas Diponegoro and Andalas University.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Satria, S. Nisworo, J. Windarta, and R. B. Y. Syah, "Performance of single axis tracker technology and automatic battery monitoring in solar hybrid systems," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 3247–3255, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.11591/eei.v12i6.5506.
- [2] B. Modu, M. P. Abdullah, M. A. Sanusi, and M. F. Hamza, "DC-based microgrid: Topologies, control schemes, and implementations," *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, vol. 70, pp. 61–92, May 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.aej.2023.02.021.

- [3] M. W. Altaf, M. T. Arif, S. N. Islam, and M. E. Haque, "Microgrid protection challenges and mitigation approaches-a comprehensive review," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 38895–38922, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3165011.
- [4] E. T. Sayed *et al.*, "Renewable energy and energy storage systems," *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 3, p. 1415, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.3390/en16031415.
- [5] A. G. Olabi and M. A. Abdelkareem, "Renewable energy and climate change," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 158, p. 112111, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2022.112111.
- [6] H. B. Tambunan, N. W. Priambodo, J. Hartono, I. A. Aditya, M. Triani, and Rasgianti, "Research trends on microgrid systems: a bibliometric network analysis," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 2529–2545, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v13i3.pp2529-2545.
- [7] T. Meenual and P. Usapein, "Microgrid policies: a review of technologies and key drivers of Thailand," *Frontiers in Energy Research*, vol. 9, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.3389/fenrg.2021.591537.
- [8] M. Ahmed, L. Meegahapola, A. Vahidnia, and M. Datta, "Stability and control aspects of microgrid architectures-a comprehensive review," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 144730–144766, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3014977.
- [9] D. E. Olivares *et al.*, "Trends in microgrid control," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 1905–1919, Jul. 2014, doi: 10.1109/TSG.2013.2295514.
- [10] K. Gao, T. Wang, C. Han, J. Xie, Y. Ma, and R. Peng, "A review of optimization of microgrid operation," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 10, p. 2842, May 2021, doi: 10.3390/en14102842.
- [11] D. Akinyele, E. Olabode, and A. Amole, "Review of fuel cell technologies and applications for sustainable microgrid systems," *Inventions*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 1–35, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.3390/inventions5030042.
- [12] B. Dey, S. Misra, and F. P. Garcia Marquez, "Microgrid system energy management with demand response program for clean and economical operation," *Applied Energy*, vol. 334, p. 120717, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.120717.
- [13] Z. Ullah *et al.*, "Implementation of various control methods for the efficient energy management in hybrid microgrid system," *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, vol. 14, no. 5, p. 101961, May 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.asej.2022.101961.
- [14] M. H. Alabdullah and M. A. Abido, "Microgrid energy management using deep Q-network reinforcement learning," *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, vol. 61, no. 11, pp. 9069–9078, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.aej.2022.02.042.
- [15] H. Satria, R. Syah, N. A. Silviana, and Syafii, "Sensitivity of solar panel energy conversion at sunrise and sunset on three weather fluctuations in equatorial climate," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 2449–2458, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v13i3.pp2449-2458.
- [16] A. S. Madona and Y. Nora, "Development of an interactive multimedia-based IPS module for grade IV elementary school students (in Indonesian)," *Jurnal Pelangi*, vol. 8, no. 2, Jun. 2016, doi: 10.22202/jp.2016.v8i2.1048.
- [17] A. P. Abido and B. Kabaso, "Energy-efficient hierarchical routing in wireless sensor networks based on fog computing," *Eurasip Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking*, vol. 2021, no. 1, p. 8, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1186/s13638-020-01835-w.
- [18] S. Ali, Z. Zheng, M. Aillerie, J. P. Sawicki, M. C. Péra, and D. Hissel, "A review of dc microgrid energy management systems dedicated to residential applications," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 14, p. 4308, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.3390/en14144308.
- [19] A. A. Kumar and N. A. Prabha, "A comprehensive review of DC microgrid in market segments and control technique," *Heliyon*, vol. 8, no. 11, p. e11694, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11694.
- [20] M. Mungkin, H. Satria, D. Maizana, M. Isa, Syafii, and M. Y. Puriza, "Analysis of the feasibility of adding a grid-connected hybrid photovoltaic system to reduce electrical load," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 1160–1171, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v14.i2.pp1160-1171.
- [21] Y. Jia, P. Wen, Y. Yan, and L. Huo, "Joint operation and transaction mode of rural multi microgrid and distribution network," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 14409–14421, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3050793.
- [22] J. P. C. Silveira, P. J. dos Santos Neto, B. C. Moura, E. R. Filho, and T. A. dos S. Barros, "Power management with BMS to modified interlinking converter topology in hybrid AC/DC microgrid," *Energy Reports*, vol. 9, pp. 1743–1765, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.egy.2022.12.082.
- [23] S. A. Shezan *et al.*, "Effective dispatch strategies assortment according to the effect of the operation for an islanded hybrid microgrid," *Energy Conversion and Management: X*, vol. 14, p. 100192, May 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.ecmx.2022.100192.
- [24] A. Muhtadi, D. Pandit, N. Nguyen, and J. Mitra, "Distributed energy resources based microgrid: review of architecture, control, and reliability," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 57, no. 3, pp. 2223–2235, May 2021, doi: 10.1109/TIA.2021.3065329.
- [25] Y. Huang, G. Li, C. Chen, Y. Bian, T. Qian, and Z. Bie, "Resilient distribution networks by microgrid formation using deep reinforcement learning," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 4918–4930, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1109/TSG.2022.3179593.
- [26] İ. Çetinbaş, B. Tamyürek, and M. Demirtaş, "Design, analysis and optimization of a hybrid microgrid system using HOMER software: Eskişehir osmangazi university example," *International Journal of Renewable Energy Development*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 65–79, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.14710/ijred.8.1.65-79.
- [27] S. K. Sahoo, A. K. Sinha, and N. K. Kishore, "Control techniques in AC, DC, and hybrid AC-DC microgrid: a review," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 738–759, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1109/JESTPE.2017.2786588.
- [28] M. Warneryd and K. Karltorp, "Microgrid communities: disclosing the path to future system-active communities," *Sustainable Futures*, vol. 4, p. 100079, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.sftr.2022.100079.
- [29] L. Che, M. Shahidehpour, A. Alabdulwahab, and Y. Al-Turki, "Hierarchical coordination of a community microgrid with AC and DC microgrids," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 3042–3051, Nov. 2015, doi: 10.1109/TSG.2015.2398853.
- [30] E. Bullich-Massagué, F. Díaz-González, M. Aragüés-Peñalba, F. Girbau-Llistuella, P. Olivella-Rosell, and A. Sumper, "Microgrid clustering architectures," *Applied Energy*, vol. 212, pp. 340–361, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.12.048.
- [31] W. Yang, X. Kang, X. Wang, and M. Wang, "MPC-based three-phase unbalanced power coordination control method for microgrid clusters," *Energy Reports*, vol. 9, pp. 1830–1841, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.egy.2022.12.079.
- [32] Mansur, S. Manjang, A. Arief, and Y. S. Akil, "Optimal hybrid renewable energy generation planning based on BSG-starcraft radius particle swarm optimization," *Przegląd Elektrotechniczny*, vol. 99, no. 2, pp. 82–87, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.15199/48.2023.02.13.
- [33] Z. Liu, X. Xu, H. A. Abdelsalam, and E. Makram, "Power system harmonics study for unbalanced microgrid system with PV sources and nonlinear loads," *Journal of Power and Energy Engineering*, vol. 03, no. 05, pp. 43–55, 2015, doi: 10.4236/jpee.2015.35004.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Habib Satria received B.Sc. degree in electrical engineering education from Padang State University in 2016, and M.T. degree in electrical engineering from University Andalas, Indonesia, in 2018 and Engineer professional (Ir). degree from Universitas Diponegoro, Indonesia, in 2022. He is currently a lecture in Dept. of Electrical Engineering, Universitas Medan Area, Indonesia. His research interests are new and renewable energy, concerning about solar power plant, automatic control system, IoT, real-time simulation, green computing and power system. He is a member of the IAENG (International Association of Engineers) and The Institution of Engineers Indonesia. He can be contacted at email: habib.satria@staff.uma.ac.id.

Rahmad B. Y. Syah is an Associate Professor in Universitas Medan Area and received head of Excellent Centre Innovations and New Science (PUIN) Universitas Medan Area. His research interests are modeling and computing, artificial intelligence, Data Science, Business Intelligent, Metaheuristics Hybrid Algorithm and Computational Intelligent. He is a member of the IEEE, Institute for System and Technologies of Information, Control, and Communication, IAENG (International Association of Engineers). He should be contacted at email: rahmadsyah@uma.ac.id.

Dadan Ramdan received a B.Sc. degree in Instrumentation Physic from the Universitas Padjadjaran in 1988, and M.Sc. degree in Instrumentation Physic from Bandung Institute of Technology, Indonesia, in 1991, and M.Eng. degree in Production System Engineering from Toyohasi University of Technology, Japan, in 2000 and a Dr. degree from Universiti Sains Malaysia in 2013. He is currently a Profesor in the Dept. of Electrical Engineering, Universitas Medan Area, Indonesia. His research metaheuristics hybrid algorithm and computational intelligent, renewable energy, automatic control system and material. He can be contacted via email: dadan@uma.ac.id.

Muhammad Khahfi Zuhanda received the B.S., M.Sc., and Ph.D. degree in mathematics from Universitas Sumatera Utara. Currently, he works as a lecturer in the Informatics Engineering Study Program, Faculty of Engineering, at the Universitas Medan Area. His research interests are broad and cover a wide range of areas in mathematics, including mathematical modelling, data science, operations research, and optimization. His work in these areas has not only broadened the horizons of mathematical knowledge but has also found practical applications in various industries and sectors. He can be contacted via email at khahfi@staff.uma.ac.id.

Jaka Windarta received a Ir. degree in Electrical Engineering from the Bandung Institute of Technology in 1988, and M.T. degree in Electrical Engineering from Bandung Institute of Technology, Indonesia, in 1995, and Dr. degree from Bogor Agricultural University, Indonesia, in 2009. He is currently a senior lecturer in the Department of Electrical Engineering and Master of Energy of Diponegoro University, Indonesia. His research interests are new and renewable energy, smart grid, and power system computation. He is a member of the IEEE. He can be contacted at email: jakawindarta@lecturer.undip.ac.id.

Syafii received a B.Sc degree in electrical engineering from the University of North Sumatera in 1997, and M.T. degree in electrical engineering from Bandung Institute of Technology, Indonesia, in 2002, and a Ph.D. degree from Universiti Teknologi Malaysia in 2011. He is currently a Professor in the Dept. of Electrical Engineering, Universitas Andalas, Indonesia. His research interests are new and renewable energy, smart grid, and power system computation. He is a member of the IEEE. He can be contacted via email: syafii@eng.unand.ac.id.

Almoataz Youssef Abdelaziz (Senior Member, IEEE) received his Ph.D. degree in electrical engineering according to channel systems between Ain Shams University and Brunel University, England, in 1996. He has served as Professor of electrical power engineering at Ain Shams University, since 2007. Currently he is assigned to the Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Future Universities in Egypt. He has authored or co-authored more than 550 refereed journal and conference papers, 45 book chapters, and six co-edited books with Elsevier, Springer, and CRC Press. He is a member of the IEC, CIGRE and CIRED Sub-Committees in Egypt. He has been awarded many awards for different research and for international publications from Ain Shams University and Future University in Egypt. He received the Ain Shams University Appreciation Award in Advanced Technology Engineering Sciences in 2022. He is the chair of the IEEE Education Society Chapter in Egypt. He is an editorial board member, editor, associate editor, and editorial advisory board member for many international journals. His research interests include the application of artificial intelligence and evolutionary and heuristic optimization techniques to the planning, operation, and control of power systems. He can be contacted at email: almoataz.abdelaziz@fue.edu.eg.